

Effective control of sheath rot (ShR) disease

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ShR, caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Saw) Gem., is a serious disease in the North Arcot District of India. We studied the efficacy of different fungicides for ShR control in a field trial using ADT35.

Table 1. Evaluation scale for ShR damage to rice in Tamil Nadu, India.

Sheath area affected	Grade
Less than 1%	1
1-5%	3
6-25%	5
26-50%	7
More than 50%	9

There were seven treatments in a randomized block design with four replications. Fungicides were sprayed 40 and 60 d after transplanting. Disease intensity was measured by selecting 10 hills at random, from which 1 tiller with maximum infection was taken for grading (Table 1).

Table 2. Efficacy of some fungicides for ShR control, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment/ha	Disease intensity (mean)	Mean yield (t/ha)	% yield increase over control	Cost ^a of treatment/ha (\$)
Tridemorph (100 ml) + carbendazim (100 g)	0.87	4.6	37.4	11.55
Tridemorph (200 ml)	1.40	4.6	36.8	8.20
Tridemorph (100 ml) + mancozeb (500 g)	2.15	4.5	34.3	10.85
Carbendazim (100 g) + mancozeb (500 g)	2.40	4.3	28.9	14.30
Carbendazim (200 g)	2.97	4.3	27.6	15.00
Mancozeb (1000 g)	4.65	4.1	22.2	14.20
Control	6.80	3.4	—	—
CD (P = 0.05)	0.73	—	—	—

^aConverted at the rate of \$1 = Rs 11.44.

All treatments significantly reduced disease intensity and significantly increased the yield over the control (Table 2). Tridemorph at 100 ml + carbendazim at 100 g/ha or tridemorph at 200 ml/ha performed best at both application dates. □

Pest control and management INSECTS

Elaphropeza, a new pupal parasite of rice gall midge (GM) in India

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During a survey of GM *Orseolia oryzae* parasites in Orissa, we found a new pupal parasite. It was identified as *Elaphropeza* sp. (Diptera: Empididae) by Dr. K. G. V. Smith of the British Museum, London. The adult *Elaphropeza* is fragile, red, and 1.5 mm long. Its abdomen is 0.5 mm long, and wings are as long as the body. The parasite occurs infrequently in rice fields and parasitized less than 1% GM pupae in the field in Oct (wet season). In other months, it was not detected. The parasite maggot attacked the GM pupa externally. Pupation took place inside the gall. The maggots occasionally behaved as hyperparasites on pupae of *Platyaster oryzae*

(Cameron), a dominant egg-larval parasite of GM in Bhubaneswar. □

Population dynamics of the brown planthopper (BPH) in the Mekong Delta

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BPH is the most important rice pest in Vietnam, particularly in the Mekong Delta. BPH outbreaks occurred in 1969, 1971, 1973, and 1974 in almost all provinces in central and southern Vietnam.

Light trap collection data and field observations in Long An (1978-79) and Tien Giang (1977-78) provinces showed that BPH are active almost all year (see figure).

Cropping pattern determines seasonal BPH population in the Mekong Delta. Rainfed and irrigated rice areas significantly differ in seasonal BPH populations. In Long An, a rainfed area, there are two annual crops grown: May-Sep and Oct-Feb. There are 10 to 11 BPH generations from May to Feb. No rice is grown between Feb and Apr.

There are about 25-30 d from 1 generation peak to the next. Two population peaks usually develop each year, one in each crop season. Peak population generally occurs at or after panicle initiation – Jul-Aug and Dec-Jan.

In Tien Giang, an irrigated area, there are three crop seasons with short-duration varieties: summer, May-Aug; autumn, Sep-Dec; and winter, Dec-Apr. There are 11-12 BPH generations/yr with 3 population peaks – Aug, Dec, and Mar.

In both areas, light-trap catches of BPH are largest 12-15 d after high nymph